

interstore

D4.3 – Data sharing valorisation concepts for validation of user acceptance

WP4 – Multiservice and Flexibility Monetisation

T4.3 – Methodology for data valorisation from connected data spaces to achieve user acceptance.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BSS	Battery Storage System
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
EV	Electric Vehicle
ESS	Energy Storage System
ENTSO-E	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HESS	Hybrid Energy Storage System
HLUC	High Level Use Case
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
METEO	Meteorological Data
MILP	Mixed-Integer Linear Programming
NPV	Net Present Value
PV	Photovoltaic
ROI	Return on Investment
SENTINEL	Sustainable Energy Transition Indicators and Links
SoC	State of the Charge
WP	Work Package
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
DSO	Distribution System Operator
TSO	Transmission System Operator
HLUC	High Level Use Case
NPV	Net Present Value
PVGIS	Photovoltaic Geographic Information System
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
OPEX	operating expense
GMM	Gaussian Mixture Model
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
BIC	Bayesian Information Criterion
OC-SVM	One Class Support Vector Machine

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report outlines the development and implementation of a suite of services designed to showcase data valorisation use cases, through connected data spaces, with a particular focus on Distributed Energy Resources (DERs). These activities are carried out under Task T4.3 of the InterSTORE project, and aim to demonstrate how the structured sharing of operational and supplementary data, can generate value for a wide range of stakeholders. Benefits include improved accuracy in asset management and predictive maintenance, increased trust in system performance, and reduced uncertainty in service delivery and investment decision-making.

The methodologies proposed in this task, along with the corresponding developed services, aim to identify key variables and determine the valuable data types to be collected, through the connected data space established in Task T4.2. These data serve as the foundation for several value creation scenarios, designed to support informed decision-making. The valorisation cases presented here are the following: i) PV Performance Evaluation Tool, ii) HESS optimal dispatch tool, iii) Green EV charging Ranking tool, iv) Battery anomaly detection model. These scenarios enable more accurate estimations of critical performance metrics such as return on investment (ROI), payback periods, and maintenance costs (including predictive models), alongside personalized recommendation systems, tailored to specific user profiles and system contexts.

A core aspect of this work is the emphasis on sharing data, derived from operational systems deployed in the project's pilot sites. By showcasing real-world performance metrics, this approach seeks to build greater awareness and acceptance of distributed energy resource solutions. The demonstration of both financial and non-financial benefits, serves as a compelling motivator for adoption, particularly among target groups such as private residential users, renewable energy communities, and commercial or industrial facility operators. In doing so, the work also differentiates between the roles of various stakeholders, acknowledging the distinct perspectives of technology adopters, system operators, and end-users.

Moreover, the methodologies explore the use of data from different perspectives. It uses a benchmark approach in the case the PV performance assessment, it uses a gamification approach in the case of the EV green charging ranking, driving users' behaviours towards a common goal, third-party data acquisition for asset optimization and yet a validation approach with the anomaly detection. In addition, it also explores how flexibility availability can be communicated in a data space environment benefiting for the transparency and data sovereignty it provides. This task is closely interlinked with other activities across the InterSTORE project. For instance, it builds on T4.2 which is dedicated to ensuring the deployment and service creation within the pilot sites. It complements Task T4.4, which focuses on assessing the broader societal impacts of energy systems and ensuring data handling practices are in line with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements, thereby reinforcing user trust. It also aligns with Task T6.3 by actively engaging stakeholders, demonstrating the tangible benefits and added value that data sharing can bring to the energy sector.

In conclusion, the outcomes of Task T4.3 include the design and implementation of a comprehensive data valorisation methodology. This work not only supports technical innovation, but also contributes to raising awareness and promoting wider acceptance of distributed energy resources. The task plays a crucial part in advancing the objectives of the InterSTORE project and facilitating the transition toward a more data-driven and decarbonised energy ecosystem.

1 Introduction

1.1 Data Valorisation in Connected Data Spaces

Data valorisation in connected data spaces is emerging as a cornerstone for achieving a more digitalized, efficient, and integrated energy system in Europe. These data spaces provide a framework for sharing and utilizing data among trusted parties, under precise rules concerning security, legal compliance, and fair remuneration. In the energy domain, they enable seamless data exchange across various stakeholders, including consumers, prosumers, grid operators, service providers, and regulators. The regulatory framework and support literature are outlined in Figure 1. It starts with the establishment of the int:net project with the 5 first layer projects and a 2nd layer of which includes InterSTORE project as well. This cluster project, supervises and coordinates the advancements of data space projects and their developments.

The Digitalization of Energy Action plan [1], sets the landscape and vision on how to extract value from data sharing, while the Data Act [2] establishes the framework for data owners to share their smart meter data beyond the Distribution system Operator (DSO)/retailers, but also aggregators/brokers. This was followed by the ENTEC [3] and EtipSNET [4] study and white paper, have provided the use cases feeding the Blueprint report [5] that captures all aspects of the architecture and governance aspects. Complemented by the Bridge report [6] on data sharing reference architecture, and identifying all European projects and coordinated actions related to Data Spaces. The recent Data4Energy (D4E) group will provide insights on how to use data and use AI in the foreseen developments, while the Insieme project will deploy data spaces in 16 European member states and advance the longed piece for ensuring the interoperability between connectors, the Data Space Protocol [7].

Figure 1: EU Regulatory framework for data space development

By leveraging data as a strategic asset, connected data spaces allow stakeholders to optimize energy production, distribution, and consumption processes. This innovation aligns with the objectives outlined in the European Union's Digitalization of Energy Action Plan [1] the European Data Act [2], focusing on enhancing renewable energy integration and advancing towards carbon neutrality goals. Key elements of data valorisation include:

- **Interoperability:** Facilitating the exchange of data across different platforms and systems.
- **Governance:** Establishing trust and transparency through robust legal and operational frameworks.
- **Efficiency:** Unlocking new opportunities for real-time decision-making and resource optimization through data-driven solutions.
- **Innovation:** Encouraging the development of new business models and services through secure and interoperable data-sharing ecosystems.

Data spaces, therefore, not only streamline technical processes, but also contribute to the creation of value chains that benefit all stakeholders, from individual consumers to large-scale energy operators.

1.2 Development of Task 4.3

This task had the vision to identify data sharing use cases that bring value to the dataspace users within the InterSTORE project. The goal was to align with other running projects such as the Enershare project, and remain consistent with the progress being made, in ETIPSNET and other Working groups in data spaces and data management. Within InterSTORE, we recognized that, sharing operational data from HESS and other distributed resources, in a connected data space, can add value to different stakeholders. It can for example, contribute to a higher accuracy in asset management and maintenance (maintenance, operation, failure detection, asset lifecycles, lifespan and costs or performance).

This task set out to show how processing shared data from running systems in the pilots, can promote user acceptance and awareness. This could be achieved by increasing trust (in system recommendations) and reducing uncertainty regarding service provision, support in investment opportunities, namely at residential level, commercial, or industrial. It will present the methodology/valorisation cases and provide examples of creating knowledge/value from the data, such as allowing a more accurate estimate of payback time, return on investment (ROI), maintenance costs (and its event prediction) and the creation of a recommendation system for manufacturers/ installers, decision support of the fittest asset solution according to the context or type of client.

Such decisions are supported on variables, which need to be identified and included in each case. The valorisation case methodology will identify the specific data, which is recognized to be more valuable and its specification to be collected by the common data spaces created in task T4.2. The demonstration of this activity through this task, will provide insights and usefulness to end users, manufacturers, installers/operators and business model design of shared data, with the intention of enabling higher adoption, increase awareness and acceptance of distributed energy resources in general.

1.3 Outline of the deliverable

The deliverable is structured to effectively communicate the essential points. Chapter 2 starts by identifying the relevant literature and project initiatives through which InterSTORE

is connected in the context of data spaces and data sharing. It further identifies, the agreed use cases and pins down those related to the InterSTORE scope, which are (DER, HESS, EVs and demand response). Chapter 3 describes the four valorisation cases developed in the project, and provides examples of the output, while explaining how the inputs are supplied by the services created in the Data Space. The four valorisation cases are:

- i) PV Performance Evaluation Tool,
- ii) HESS optimal dispatch tool,
- iii) Green EV charging Ranking tool,
- iv) Battery anomaly detection model.

Chapter 4 presents the flexibility availability use case, which although not a direct valorisation case itself, ended up being a way of demonstrating the new features of the new InterSTORE connector developments, related to the “push mechanism” and the “blockchain mechanisms”. It presents how data can be pushed for a “market like” collection of asset’s flexibility availabilities, and shows how the demonstration occurred within InterSTORE, between an aggregator acting partner, and a flexibility provider acting partner.

Chapter 5 concludes the deliverable by reflecting on limitations of the existing cases and outlining future work to be done in this domain. Moreover, it highlights the unleashed potential of the new features of the InterSTORE connector.

2 Test and verify models

2.1 High Level Use cases and European alignment

The primary objectives of data utilization in connected data spaces focus on driving innovation, enhancing operational efficiency, and achieving sustainability in the energy domain. These objectives align with the High-Level Use Cases (HLUCs) identified by the ETIP SNET [4] and further expanded in the Blueprint CEEDS report [5], which demonstrate practical applications of data-driven solutions to address key challenges in the energy transition. The following areas are highlighted:

Integration of Renewable Energy Sources: By providing real-time data exchange capabilities, data spaces facilitate the integration of distributed energy resources (DERs), such as solar panels, wind turbines, and battery storage into the grid. This supports Flexibility Provision by Buildings, Districts, and Industrial Processes, where local resources contribute to grid stability and energy optimization. Additionally, large-scale renewable integration aligns with Pan-European Wholesale Markets and Regional and Local Markets, enhancing cross-border energy exchanges.

Consumer Empowerment: Data spaces enable consumers to actively participate in energy markets through mechanisms such as demand response and local energy communities. This supports End-user Market Participation, empowering consumers with tools to monitor, control, and share their data securely. By fostering transparency and engagement, data spaces promote trust and incentivize active participation in sustainability efforts.

Operational Optimization: Improved data sharing allows grid operators to manage congestion, optimize grid performance, and enhance system reliability. These capabilities support Market-driven Transmission system Operator (TSO)–DSO–System User Interactions, where enhanced coordination between transmission and distribution systems enables efficient grid management. This also includes Digitalization and Automation of Grid Operations, leveraging technologies such as AI and predictive analytics for smarter grid operations.

Cross-Sectoral Synergies Data spaces enable smart sector integration, linking electricity with gas, heating, cooling, and transportation systems. This interconnected approach improves resource efficiency and accelerates decarbonization, as highlighted in Smart Sector Integration use case. Sector coupling facilitates the optimization of multi-energy systems, creating synergies that reduce emissions and enhance energy security.

Data-driven Innovation: By unlocking the potential of big data, artificial intelligence (AI), and advanced analytics, data spaces drive innovation in energy services and applications. These innovations support Interconnected Flexibility Markets, fostering collaboration across markets to improve flexibility and resilience. Additionally, the creation of new business models and services is aligned with Dynamic Energy Communities and Local Energy Systems, which emphasizes the value of localized energy solutions.

2.2 Objectives of Data Utilization within InterSTORE

The high-level use cases outlined in the previous sub-chapter 2.1, illustrate how connected data spaces act as a backbone for innovation, resilience, and sustainability in the energy sector. They support the EU's carbon neutrality goals, while providing tangible benefits for consumers, operators, and policymakers. By integrating these high-level use cases into data utilization strategies, stakeholders can unlock new opportunities for growth and collaboration, ensuring a sustainable and consumer-centric energy future for Europe.

Sharing and using data from third-party users and resources through a European connected data space, allows trustworthiness, data sovereignty, integrity and authentication. In InterSTORE, and aligned with the above HLUC, we've set the following four main objectives among others:

1. Provide information for decision support
2. Provide inputs for Optimization models or system modeling
3. Test, verification and evaluation of assets and system performance
4. Enable federated learning for Machine Learning models

In T4.3 we set out to develop at least four cases, that leverage data shared among the partners. In this context, we present one example for each of the four objectives stated above. Each case is described, and an actual simulation is provided, using real shared data from the consortium within the data space.

The several valorisation cases are, hence described with a dedicated sub-chapter to each case. An additional use case is also provided, which was specifically designed for flexibility availability provision to an Aggregator. This last use case, was designed to showcase how the new developments in the InterSTORE connector were applied. The new developments feature the option to publish data transactions on the blockchain, and the new push mechanism, used to spontaneously publish data on a third-party created service. This demonstrated use case, shows how it can unleash the potential for data spaces, to be a backbone for market creation mechanism to support grid service provision.

3 InterSTORE valorisation cases

The InterSTORE project implemented a data space designed to integrate and optimize three primary assets: batteries, photovoltaic systems (PV), and electric vehicle (EV) chargers. The developed data space leverages on these assets, through advanced data sharing and analysis to enhance energy performance, operational efficiency, and value creation.

To complement the core data, additional services were integrated into the data space, using relevant datasets. These datasets were curated and enhanced through partnerships with industry leaders, researchers, and technology providers.

Additional datasets were integrated into the data space to provide critical support for decision-making and optimization, these are:

Operational data from batteries: Dispatch recommendations from lithium and vanadium batteries were collected to improve energy storage efficiency and flexibility. The case focuses on optimizing grid integration and supporting renewable energy systems.

Operational data from PV: Operational data from photovoltaic systems was analysed to identify performance inefficiencies and maximize energy output

Operational data from EVs: Data from EV chargers were analysed to optimize charging schedules and reduce grid stress during peak demand. Integration of this dataset enabled the development of smart charging solutions, contributing to enhanced EV penetration and improved user experience.

Weather Forecast: Used for PV generation predictions and optimizing battery performance.

Emission Coefficients: Employed to assess the carbon footprint of energy usage, enabling environmentally conscious decision-making.

Electricity Prices: Integrated to facilitate cost-effective energy trading and consumption strategies.

Flexibility Data: Shared by batteries to enhance grid reliability and support demand-response programs.

All services and related responsible partners, as well as the source of data is summarized in Error! Reference source not found..

Service No.	Dataset/Services	Partners	Source/Details
1	Data from battery operation	Capwatt	From assets BMS
2	Data from battery operation	ENELX	From assets BMS
3	Data from battery operation	FZJ	From assets BMS
4	Operational data from PV	Capwatt	From local SCADA
5	Operational data from PV	FZJ	From local SCADA
6	Operational data from EV chargers	Capwatt	From assets' EMS
7	Operational data from EV chargers	ENELX	From assets' EMS
8	Weather forecast	InescTEC	SENTINEL/METEO Galicia
9	Emissions coefficients of electricity mix for 5 project zones	INESCTEC	SENTINEL, Electricity Maps
10	Day ahead average emissions of electricity mix for Portugal	INESCTEC	SENTINEL

11	Current day average emissions of the electricity mix for 5 project zones	INESCTEC	Electricity Maps
12	Electricity prices (DA)	INESCTEC	ENTSO-E
13	Flexibility available from batteries	INESCTEC/Cybergrid	Battery operational data as sources

Table 1: Services created in the dataspace within InterSTORE.

Having all the services created in D4.2, the four valorization cases were developed and hereafter explained. These are: i) PV Performance Evaluation Tool, ii) HESS optimal dispatch tool, iii) Green EV charging Ranking tool, iv) Battery anomaly detection model.

3.1 PV Performance Evaluation Tool

An example for the first objective (Provide information for decision support), can be demonstrated using the PV systems which were used in the project. Maximizing the efficiency of photovoltaic (PV) panels is essential for achieving both energy and environmental goals in the transition to a sustainable future. PV panels offer a clean alternative to fossil fuels, but their performance varies widely due to factors such as geographic location, panel technology, and installation quality. This variability often leaves users without a reliable way to evaluate the optimal performance of their systems.

The PV Valorisation Tool bridges this gap by enabling users to benchmark their PV systems against tailored performance standards based on their specific technology and location. By comparing actual energy outputs to these benchmarks, users can identify inefficiencies, take corrective actions, and ultimately maximize energy production. In the case of a Renewable energy community or neighborhood, the benchmark can be the median value of the participants.

This tool is particularly beneficial for organizations managing multiple installations, as it fosters transparency by allowing comparative performance analysis across different locations. Homeowners, businesses, and corporate clients can also use it to optimize system performance, reduce maintenance costs, and demonstrate commitment to renewable energy strategies. For corporate users, the tool serves as a key differentiator in markets where sustainability is a competitive advantage.

Key Objectives:

- **Performance Benchmarking:** Compare PV energy output with expected performance based on panel technology, installation type, and geographic location.
- **Financial Analysis:** Assess the net present value (NPV) and long-term economic viability of installations, helping users make informed investment decisions.

3.1.1 Methodology

The methodology for the tool leverages estimation of generation and comparisons of system performance to support informed decisions that reduce wasted potential. This structured approach combines real-world data, user inputs, and financial analysis.

1. **Data Input for PV Performance:** the user is requested to provide a set of information regarding their PV system, these include the monthly energy outputs of the system in kWh, as shown in the WebApp dedicated section in [Figure 2](#).

Technical Performance Analysis:

January [kWh]:	May [kWh]:	September [kWh]:
<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>
February [kWh]:	June [kWh]:	October [kWh]:
<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>
March [kWh]:	July [kWh]:	November [kWh]:
<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>
April [kWh]:	August [kWh]:	December [kWh]:
<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>

Figure 2: PV performance tool inputs required in the WebApp

2. **Benchmark:** For the benchmark values, used to conduct the performance comparison, the tool uses the PVGIS' tool application programming interface (API), to calculate the expected PV system output based on the users' inputs. The installed power in kW, the latitude and longitude of the PV panels, as well as the slope and azimuth, all in degrees are required. Finally, the tool also requires the user to define the losses in percentage and to choose one of the available PV panel technologies. All of this information is requested through the interface shown in Figure 3, part the dedicated WebApp.

Installed Power [kW]:	Slope [°]:
<input type="text" value="1"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Latitude [°]:	Azimuth [°]:
<input type="text" value="40.000"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Longitude [°]:	Losses [%]:
<input type="text" value="-5.000"/>	<input type="text" value="0"/>

CrystSi: Crystalline Silicon.
 CIS: Copper Indium (gallium) Selenide.
 CdTe: Cadmium Telluride.

Technology

You selected: Unknown

Figure 3: PV performance tool inputs required in the WebApp

3. **Financial Analysis:** For this analysis the user needs to provide the following information, the estimated annual operating cost, OPEX, in percentage, the installed power in kW, the discount rate in percentage, the project or installation expected lifetime in

years, the initial investment cost in euros (€), and the average, minimum and maximum expected annual cash flows, also in euros (€). The necessary inputs are requested in a dedicated section and can be seen in [Figure 4](#).

Financial Performance Analysis:

Estimated annual opex [%]:

1.00

Installed Power [kW]:

1

Discount Rate [%]:

1

Average Annual Cash Flow [€]:

0

Project Lifetime [years]:

1

Minimum Annual Cash Flow [€]:

0

Initial Investment [€]:

0

Maximum Annual Cash Flow [€]:

0

Calculate Financial Analysis

Figure 4: PV financial inputs required in the WebApp

3.1.2 Expected Results Example

- PV Performance Analysis Tool:** The values shown in [Figure 5](#) are an example output provided by the tool, showing the format of the output. In the example provided, one can observe on the right side, the actual user Energy Output of the PV system, over the assessed months, and the estimated optimal generation from the reference scenario on the left side. It shows in this case that the system is generating around 1% less, when compared to the reference scenario.

OUTPUTS:

Figure 5: PV performance tool generation output

- Financial Analysis Tool: The values shown in Figure 6, are an example of the installation financial indicators for the inputs provided. It shows the output generated, the capital expenditure (CAPEX), operational expenditure (OPEX) and corresponding Payback period, if the reference and optimal generation occurs.

OUTPUTS:

According to the inputs you provided, and comparing with the average values for residential installations:

CAPEX: 213.33333333333334 €/kWp ↑ 1186.6666666666667	OPEX: 2.1333333333333333 €/kWp ↑ 2.8666666666666667	Payback Period 10.828282828282827 years ↓ -2.828282828282827
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Figure 6: PV financial tool analysis output

3.2 HESS Optimal dispatch tool

For the second objective defined (Provide inputs for Optimization models or system modeling), we provide an example focused on optimal dispatch of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS). The optimization of HESS presents a significant opportunity to reduce energy supply costs and minimize environmental impacts, while addressing the challenges of renewable energy integration. This valorisation case makes use of federated data collected from SENTINEL. It applies a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) optimization model to evaluate the performance of HESS, compared to single-battery systems, focusing on two key objectives: cost minimization (EUR/kWh) and emission reduction (gCO_{2eq}/kWh).

3.2.1 Key Features of the Optimization Model

The key features of the optimization model include the evaluation of a wide range of energy storage technologies, such as lithium-ion batteries, vanadium redox flow batteries, lead-acid batteries, nickel-cadmium batteries, sodium-sulfur batteries, flywheels, and supercapacitors. The model utilizes real-world data from an industrial building, incorporating forecasted load profiles and day-ahead market prices. The model integrates constraints including battery capacity, power limits, and degradation linearization to ensure realistic and actionable outcomes.

The metrics analysed by the model include cost metrics, where energy supply costs in euros per kilowatt-hour and life cycle costs are calculated as key components. Environmental metrics, are also assessed through a cradle-to-grave life cycle assessment, to provide a comprehensive view of the environmental impact. Additionally, battery degradation is modelled based on the depth of discharge and lifecycle costs, offering insights into operational efficiency and the longevity of the energy storage systems.

3.2.2 Results

The MILP optimization model demonstrates the following:

- Cost Reduction: HESS configurations, particularly lithium-supercapacitor systems, achieved the lowest total costs, demonstrating their potential for cost-efficient energy storage solutions.

- **Emission Reduction:** Hybrid systems consistently outperformed single-battery systems in reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. For example, lithium-supercapacitor combinations achieved a 2.4% reduction in emissions compared to conventional systems.
- **Battery Degradation:** HESS exhibited lower degradation rates and costs, particularly for vanadium-based technologies, due to their linear degradation profile.

The tool was developed as a microservice, as part of the larger InescTEC's Home Energy Management System (HEMS), and a dedicated WebApp was created in the project. It was released as open-source software and used as a valorization case. The WebApp can be found here: <http://InterSTORE-dev.inesctec.pt:3000/admin/home>. Figure 7 shows the front end of the tool.

Simulation parameters

Maximum power kW:

Maximum capacity kWh:

Efficiency %:

Initial Soc %:

LOAD PARAMETERS

Minimize Cost Minimize CO2

One technology simulation Two technologies simulation

Expected load forecast - kW

0H	4	1H	62	2H	35	3H	29
4H	82	5H	8	6H	13	7H	49
8H	9	9H	57	10H	100	11H	23
12H	79	13H	71	14H	36	15H	39
16H	99	17H	43	18H	45	19H	101
20H	42	21H	12	22H	98	23H	16

Expected day ahead market prices - €/kWh

0H	3.99	1H	2.92	2H	3.93	3H	2.26
4H	2.32	5H	1.83	6H	1.25	7H	0.41
8H	1.30	9H	3.35	10H	0.49	11H	1.01
12H	1.44	13H	3.81	14H	2.48	15H	4.21
16H	2.33	17H	3.54	18H	2.02	19H	3.86
20H	2.71	21H	1.21	22H	4.39	23H	2.15

Figure 7: HESS dispatch load and incentives Inputs – Screenshot of the WebApp

The user is requested to insert the expected load to be served by the battery system. This can be inserted based on an hourly basis, with a value in kW for each dedicated field. Additionally, two types of incentive: the cost per kWh, which can be the cost/kWh cleared for the day-ahead market or the expected day-ahead average $\text{gCO}_{2\text{eq}}/\text{kWh}$.

In the left side of the screen, shown in Figure 7, the user may provide the general settings of his hybrid system, here highlighted in Figure 8. The required fields for each are: Maximum Power in kW, the maximum battery capacity in kWh, the efficiency of the system in %, and the initial state of charge (SOC).

The users are required to choose 2 from 7 available technologies: Lithium, Vanadium, Acid batteries, Nickel-Cadmium, Sodium Sulphur, Flywheel and Supercapacitors.

Once the input settings are provided and the choice of the battery types is made, the user may push the set parameters button and press the run button.

The joint dispatch, will consider the degradation in terms of cost of the battery and its carbon foot-print. The degradation will be monetized and accounted in the result of the optimization function, which is presented in the output.

The cost is provided along with the corresponding chart for the joint dispatch, and can be compared with a single battery dispatch, with the charts displayed side-by-side.

Three costs (or emissions) are shown for comparison. The first is the term related to the energy component, which means the cost of consuming energy at the charging hours according to the optimal dispatch. This energy already considers the losses incurred by the system. The same stands for the emissions option. The second term, is the cost related term attributed to the degradation of the hybrid system. Lastly, the total cost and emissions are presented as a sum of these two previous terms.

Figure 8: HESS settings

The output is shown in Figure 9 with distinct colours, showing the joint dispatch on the right side of the screenshot of the WebApp, and the single dispatch on the left side.

Figure 9: Output of the HESS dispatch tool (single battery on the left, and hybrid battery dispatch on the right)

In the displayed scenario in which a Vanadium battery (10kW and 40kWh, 89% efficiency and 20% initial SOC) and a second Lithium battery (100kW, 100kWh, 88% efficiency and 20% SOC) are used, the obtained result is the one shown in Figure 8. It can be seen that the hybrid dispatch for that day, with such parameters, results in a total cost of 1663.3€, which is lower when compared to a single dispatch of 2408.43€. Which despite having a greater degradation cost, compensates, due to higher relative weight, of the energy-related cost.

3.2.3 Implications for Data Valorisation

The results underscore how the integration of real-world data into optimization models enhances the value of energy storage systems, by supporting decision-making processes for system configuration and deployment. This integration enables scenario analysis to evaluate trade-offs between cost, emissions, and degradation, providing a comprehensive understanding of system performance. Additionally, it informs investment decisions with precise insights into operational efficiency and sustainability, ensuring that energy storage solutions align with both economic and environmental objectives.

This work aligns with the objectives of Task T4.3 by demonstrating how data valorisation can drive the adoption of HESS. By leveraging connected data spaces and the optimization framework, stakeholders such as manufacturers, installers, and end-users, can gain a better understanding of the value of hybrid configurations and how to operate them efficiently, leading to increased awareness, trust, and acceptance of these systems.

3.3 Green EV Ranking Tool

Regarding the third objective (Test, verification and evaluation of assets and system performance), we chose to follow a gamification approach. An evaluation of the charging sessions of the EV users in the projects member's organizations was conducted, and compared against each other, to assess green charging behavior. Electric vehicles (EVs) are a cornerstone of sustainable transportation, but the environmental impact of charging them depends significantly on the carbon intensity of the electricity grid. Carbon intensity (measured in grams of CO₂ per kilowatt-hour) fluctuates throughout the day, based on the proportion of renewable and non-renewable energy sources in the electricity mix. This project focuses on comparing EV charging practices with the goal of minimizing emissions, by leveraging data on grid carbon intensity across regions and times.

The Green EV Ranking Tool, empowers companies and individuals to align their charging practices with environmental goals. By analyzing emissions associated with EV charging in different regions, the tool identifies optimal charging strategies and ranks organizations based on their carbon efficiency.

This application is particularly valuable for businesses operating in multiple regions with varying grid intensities. It enables these organizations to evaluate and optimize the environmental impact of their EV fleets, while fostering transparency in sustainability reporting. Companies can leverage the ranking system to demonstrate their commitment to emissions reduction, gaining a competitive edge in markets where environmental performance is a critical differentiator.

Key Objectives:

- Emissions Analysis: Quantify the carbon footprint of EV charging across different regions and times.
- Comparative Scenarios: Simulate optimal and suboptimal charging strategies to highlight opportunities for improvement.

- Performance Ranking: Develop company-specific rankings based on environmental metrics, fostering accountability and competition.
- Interactive Decision Support: Provide visual tools to analyze data and support strategic decisions for EV fleet operations.

3.3.1 Methodology

The methodology and data integration for the case study, implement a comprehensive approach that highlights effective data valorisation through several steps.

Data collection and integration involve the utilization of the Electricity Map API to obtain region-specific hourly carbon intensity data, measured in grams of CO₂ per kilowatt-hour. Charging profiles from multiple organizations are integrated alongside a combination of real-time and historical data to enhance the robustness of the analysis.

The analysis framework includes the implementation of emission calculations using standardized formulas, where hourly emissions are calculated by multiplying carbon intensity by charging volume, and daily emissions are computed through the aggregation of hourly values. Scenario simulations are developed to identify the best and worst-case charging patterns, and performance scoring mechanisms are created to evaluate the practices of different companies.

3.3.2 Web Application use and Visualization

This section will provide a real-world example, including screenshots, showing the WebApp created for this purpose, explaining the necessary inputs and to illustrate the results.

Step 1: Selecting Zones and Date

- The user starts by selecting three zones out of a selection, in this case of locations, which correspond to the InterSTORE pilots (e.g., PT, DE, FR, IT) and a specific date to which perform the analysis (e.g., 2024-11-27). The application retrieves hourly carbon intensity data for the chosen zones, which is provided by InescTEC's data space service. The section of this user interface can be seen in [Figure 10](#).

Electric Vehicle Charging Impact Analysis

This web application analyzes carbon emissions based on the charging values of different companies. You can input hourly charging values for each company and see the carbon emission rankings based on calculated scores.

Carbon Intensities for Each Zone

Select the date for analysis

2025/03/25

Select exactly 3 countries

PT x IT x DE x

Figure 10: EV green charging ranking tool dashboard

Step 2: Viewing Carbon Intensity

- Upon selection of the locations, a table is displayed with the hourly carbon intensity for each selected zone, accompanied by a bar charts for visual interpretation as can be seen in [Figure 11](#). The data can be downloaded as a CSV by clicking the dedicated icon on the table.

Select exactly 3 countries

PT x IT x DE x

Zone	0: gCO2/kWh	1: gCO2/kWh	2: gCO2/kWh	3: gCO2/kWh	4: gCO2/kWh	5: gCO2/kWh	6: gCO2/kWh	7
PT	95	124	122	119	116	119	118	
IT	448	452	450	449	440	420	419	
DE	475	489	487	497	499	497	495	

Figure 11: EV green charging ranking tool carbon intensity inputs

Step 3: Inputting Charging Profiles

- The user is then requested to upload a CSV file with the charging sessions of its infrastructure, in order to be assessed. It needs to provide the file with the format shown in Figure 12.

Charging Values for Each Company

Upload a CSV file

Drag and drop file here
Limit 200MB per file • CSV

Browse files

CSV Info

Using default values for the companies:

	Hour	Company 1 (kW)	Company 2 (kW)	Company 3 (kW)
	0	9	11	9
	1	3	10	0
	2	0	4	4
	3	8	3	7
	4	9	3	7
	5	4	11	1
	6	5	10	8
	7	1	11	12
	8	10	4	8
	9	6	3	2
	10	5	2	6

Figure 12: EV green charging ranking tool energy inputs from charging sessions

Step 4: Emission Calculation Results

- The application calculates the daily emissions for each organization in each zone. Results are presented in absolute terms, meaning that the tool considers how much an organization's charging session deviated from the most green and the worst scenario. According to this assessment it ranks them all on a table, with the option to be downloaded as a CSV file. The assessment can be performed over different time windows and it presents a gamification approach to demand response, incentivizing organizations to promote actions with their users, to achieve a goal. The incentive in this case is environmental, but it can be any other (e.g. cost). The output is shown in Figure 13.

Overall Company Ranking

	Company	Score	% away from Best Scenario	% away from Worst Scenario
0	Company 1	▲ 0.25	8.1191	18.6299
1	Company 2	▲ 0.10	0.9374	7.7582
2	Company 3	▲ 0.02	0.2239	8.1009

Figure 13: EV green charging ranking tool output according to best sustainable behaviour

3.3.3 Results

The Green EV Ranking tool provides a robust platform for analyzing and improving EV charging practices. By identifying charging times and locations with lower carbon intensity, it enables users to:

- Optimize energy use and reduce greenhouse gas emissions associated with EV fleets.
- Benchmark organizational performance in sustainability efforts, promoting accountability and competition.
- Enhance decision-making processes by integrating real-time data with strategic planning.

This tool offers additional value by supporting multi-regional operations, allowing businesses to tailor their charging strategies to the specific carbon profiles of different locations. Furthermore, the ranking system provides a means for organizations to demonstrate their commitment to reducing carbon footprints, thereby strengthening their environmental credentials in increasingly competitive markets.

3.3.4 Implications for Data Valorisation

The implementation of the Green EV Ranking tool highlights several critical aspects of successful data valorisation, including the importance of standardized data collection and integration processes, which ensure consistency and reliability across different datasets. It also emphasizes the value of real-time data access for operational decision-making, enabling timely and informed responses to dynamic conditions. The role of interactive visualization is underscored, as it makes complex data accessible and actionable for a wide range of stakeholders. Additionally, the case demonstrates the significance of comparative analytics in driving behavioural change, by providing benchmarks and insights that foster improved practices.

Overall, the case exemplifies how connected data spaces can deliver tangible business value, while aligning with environmental sustainability goals, serving as a robust model for future data valorisation initiatives in the energy sector.

3.4 Anomaly detection

An example for the fourth stated objective (Federated learning for Machine Learning models), we focused on an anomaly detection algorithm for batteries. To develop this valorisation case, we've followed an unsupervised approach when working the data. This is a particular case bringing value to users, since faulty data is expensive to obtain and hence to verify its performance. Also, the necessary data in terms of variables, number of observations and

their correlation-matrix are useful information to have, and that can be applied/used by other systems if certain considerations are met.

3.4.1 Methodology

To develop this case, InescTEC gained access to a vanadium Redox Flow battery (VRFB) dataset, that suffered, a non-catastrophic failure. This meant that the battery system kept working with abnormal behaviour. These types of malfunctioning can occur due to issues like a faulty electrolyte membrane inside the Vanadium battery deposit, a fault in a relay or other, which can lead to an erratic behaviour of the battery. In this case the log files were retrieved from the local battery management systems (BMS) and the time window under which the failure occurred was considered. The dataset was split into two sub datasets, one prior to the failure (dataset A) and another after the failure (dataset B). The fact that the failure was non-catastrophic enabled the battery to keep operating under abnormal conditions, resulting in an abnormal performance, providing a valuable dataset for validation. The Vanadium Redox Flow Battery dataset was analysed before and after a non-catastrophic failure. The dataset was divided into as can be seen in Figure 14:

- Dataset A: Normal pre-failure observations (74,992 samples).
- Dataset B: Anomalous post-failure observations (130,543 samples).

The development was done in python using the libraries Scikit learn OC-SVM and GMM We started by analysing the covariance matrix. Then we saw that the dataset was multipolar, which indicated that the GMM would apply. To find the correct number of components or clusters the AIC and BIC metrics were used, which evaluate the goodness of fit.

The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) are metrics used to evaluate the goodness of fit for statistical models. These criteria help in model selection by balancing the model's complexity against its fit to the data. The lower the values obtained for the AIC and BIC metrics, the better fit to the gaussian mixture is obtained. The number of components or clusters is hence found by minimizing these indicators. The number of components used for the model was 6.

Figure 14: Dataset A with normal observations and Dataset B after fault occurred (abnormal observations)

We performed the anomaly classification using the GMM approach first using as test the Dataset B to obtain the true positives, and then used the dataset A to perform the classification to understand if it would classify the original data all as normal observations. As a threshold we used the minimum value of likelihood of the trained model. At a second stage

we used the OC-SVM algorithm and trained the model only with the normal observation log-likelihoods. We followed the same testing procedure with both datasets A and B and compared performances.

3.4.2 Results

Figure 15 shows the components (clusters) of the GMM considered, with an example of the DC Power of the battery and average voltage in phase 1. Two regions stand out for the nominal power that the battery was operating at the time. These are charging at 2000 W and discharging at 2000 W. A third region in the middle corresponds to the moments in which the battery was close to zero or not operating at all.

In the scatter plot with 6 clusters, the x-axis represents the Battery DC Power, while the y-axis represents the average voltage of phase 1 at the energy analyzer measurement point. The left super cluster is mainly composed of clusters 1, 3 and 4 while the right super cluster is composed of cluster's 2 and 5. The cluster 0 presents observations exactly at 0 power.

Figure 15: Cluster scatter plot of the GMM model

Figure 16 shows an example of how the single Gaussians adjust to the real data from Dataset A. It's possible to observe the 6 clusters, formed by the optimization of maximizing the likelihood, having as decision variables the mean and standard deviation of each Gaussian. The example is provided for the DC voltage variable in the form of histogram. It should be noted that the overall Gaussian model curve in green, does not capture all observations represented by the density curve. However, it's the optimized approximation.

Figure 16: Histogram for Dataset A (training dataset) for the DC Voltage variable (x-axis Value), showing the 6 components and the resulting overall Gaussian Mixture curve.

To assess the effectiveness of the GMM clustering, we evaluated key statistical metrics for Dataset A and Dataset B. Table 2 presents the main characteristics obtained from the GMM application, including the total log-likelihood, its minimum and maximum values, and model selection criteria such as the AIC and BIC. These values provide insight into the clustering performance and model complexity across both datasets and are here summarized.

Metric from GMM application	Dataset A	Dataset B
Total log-likelihood GMM:	-355806.38	-85508188.42
Min value of log-likelihood	-202.13	-12392.25
Max value of log-likelihood	0.39	-7.27
Number of Parameters:	467.0	
AIC	712546.76	
BIC	716854.90	

Table 2: Main characteristics of the GMM Dataset A clusterization

Figure 17 presents the histogram of the corresponding observations' frequency, and the threshold defined. The GMM's model achieved an accuracy of 65.8% when classifying the abnormal observations (dataset B). However, when submitting dataset A to the model, it classified 100% of the observations as normal. This was expected, because the threshold was manually defined to have the minimum value of likelihood of the training dataset A (-202.13), hence all values above would be normal. However, choosing another threshold to force all abnormal observations from dataset B, to be classified 100% as anomalies, would mean choosing the maximum likelihood value generated of dataset B (-7.29). When applying this threshold instead to dataset A, there was an 11.6% misclassification rate of ground truth normal labels, into anomalies, hence, resulting in False Positives.

This means that adjusting the threshold to increase true positives, results losing accuracy in classifying normal observations (increasing false positives). This is an unfruitful trade-off as it does not improve the precision of the model. Such an approach revealed to be a limitation, since it relies on a subjective decision by the user, when defining the threshold, resulting in undesired false positives or worse, false negatives. The latter being more dangerous to the equipment since it would be generating abnormal observations without being detected.

Figure 17: Histogram of Dataset B classification using GMM

In order to solve this, we've put forward an adaptive threshold approach. We then trained the OC-SVM model with the log-likelihood values generated by the initial training of the GMM. Following the same procedure of testing both datasets (A and B), allow for a direct comparison of accuracy between the models as can be seen in Table 3. The parameters used for the OC-SVM algorithms were (nu=0.001, kernel="rbf", gamma=0.01). The training dataset is always dataset A.

Approaches and testing procedures	Accuracy
GMM/OC-SVM by testing dataset B - True Positives	98.64%
GMM/OC-SVM by testing dataset B - False negatives	0.14%
GMM/OC-SVM by testing dataset A - True negatives	99.85%
GMM/OC-SVM by testing dataset A - False Positives	0.15%
Manual threshold - GMM using the minimum Likelihood value from dataset A as threshold and testing dataset B - True Positives	65.84%
Manual threshold - GMM using the maximum likelihood value generated from dataset B as threshold and testing dataset A - False Positives	11.61%

Table 3: Accuracy comparison between manual threshold definition (GMM) and adaptive (GMM/OC-SVM)

The table highlights the superior accuracy of coupling GMM with the OC-SVM algorithm. It provides an accuracy of 98.64% of true positives classification, contrasting with 65.84% when using only the GMM approach. In fact, when analysing a full abnormal observations dataset (Dataset B) the model only classified 0.14% observations as normal (False negatives).

In Figure 18, the results of the test for dataset B with 130543 observations is shown. The model imposes a threshold derived from a kernel function, which learned from the normal likelihood values, and is able to determine what is the decision boundary to separate the observation classes. The figure presents a trimmed x-axis (from -100 to 10) to capture the nuances of the boundary. As it can be seen, the function does not perfectly classify all observations as anomalies.

Figure 18: Dataset B classification with the OC-SVM showing the decision boundary

This could occur because the likelihood values are, in fact, normal, given that the original variables of those specific observations could be consonant with the correlation matrix. In fact, it must be acknowledged that the battery kept working, and some observations (of the 1777 corresponding to 1.34%) could be derived from the system attempting to restore normal operation. Another explanation is simply a limitation of the kernel in drawing a perfect function that could capture this small percentage of false negatives. It does nevertheless have a significantly higher accuracy when compared to the GMM.

Figure 19 shows the resulting decision boundary with classified observations from Dataset A with 74992. Only 0.15% (116) of the normal observations were classified as anomalies (False positives). Similarly to the test performed with dataset B, it's clear that not all observations are classified in this case as normal ones as it is seen by the existence of red dots.

Figure 19: Dataset A classification with the OC-SVM showing the decision boundary

The assumption that dataset A followed a perfectly normal distribution when applying the GMM, is one that entails an associated accepted error. As can be seen in Figure 19, not all observations are captured by the overall GMM. It was hence expected that the classification would not be flawless. The OC-SVM nevertheless, performs very well in this regard, having improved the accuracy substantially.

3.4.3 Implications for Data Valorisation

One of the key value propositions in this case is the ability to derive meaningful insights from unlabelled or weakly labelled datasets. Since abnormal or faulty operating conditions are rare and costly to replicate under controlled circumstances, the ability to detect such anomalies using unsupervised methods like GMM and OC-SVM demonstrates a crucial advantage. This approach enhances the intrinsic value of existing data by extracting patterns that would otherwise remain hidden without labor-intensive manual labelling.

The proposed methodology, specifically the analysis of correlation structures, Gaussian Mixture Model fitting, and adaptive OC-SVM thresholding, establishes a framework that can be generalised to other types of energy storage systems or even different industrial processes. Given that the underlying principle relies on likelihood distributions rather than hard-coded thresholds or supervised labels, this makes the solution modular and adaptable to similar use cases. The reuse of the covariance matrix and model selection principles can assist other federated nodes or institutions to deploy anomaly detection mechanisms with minimal recalibration.

The overall structure of the proposed solution supports decentralised model training. As demonstrated, only statistical distributions (e.g., likelihoods, cluster memberships) are necessary for further model enhancement, which aligns well with federated learning protocols that avoid the exchange of raw data.

4 Flexibility Availability Case

4.1 Flexibility estimation

This section describes the implementation of the flexibility estimation function of a battery system. The function is designed to identify the flexibility offered by a battery energy storage system (BESS), ensuring compliance with operational constraints, while enhancing grid integration and efficiency. This implementation is critical for enabling the BESS to adapt dynamically to energy market demands, renewable energy fluctuations, and grid stability requirements. This flexibility estimation was then used to provide availability to an Aggregator role, making use of the newly developed data space connector features in InterSTORE.

The push-data mechanism is designed to publish results directly into the data space in real-time or near real-time. Data space serves as a repository and exchange platform for operational insights. The push mechanism enables:

Transparency: Stakeholders can access real-time flexibility data to make informed decisions.

Collaboration: Grid operators and market participants can use the data for demand-response planning, grid balancing, and market transactions.

Scalability: The system can integrate additional datasets, such as weather forecasts and market prices, to enhance future optimizations.

The integration of the push data mechanism ensures the optimized results of a BESS flexibility are accessible in the data space, fostering collaboration, transparency, and operational efficiency.

The integration of this functionality within a BESS demonstrates the potential for advanced energy management systems to address challenges in renewable energy integration. By maximizing flexibility, the system enables:

- **Improved Renewable Utilization:** Better alignment of storage operations with intermittent renewable energy generation.

- **Cost Efficiency:** Reduction in operational costs through optimized energy storage usage and participation in demand-response programs.
- **Sustainability:** Enhanced support for decarbonization efforts through improved grid reliability and the integration of low-carbon energy sources.

Figure 20 shows the flexibility estimation from the initial dispatch of the BESS. The top chart shows the State of charge at every moment of the daily dispatched time window. The second chart shows how the battery behaves (whether it charges or discharges). According to these setpoints and the remaining SOC, we can estimate the remaining capacity to be offered as flexibility in the last chart. Note that the flexibility availability is always in the same direction as the initial dispatch, as the battery cannot charge and discharge at the same time. It also assumes that the provided availability is accepted and cleared in order to have a ground truth for the next time step in terms of SOC.

Figure 20: Initial dispatch and available flexibility assessment for the CapWatt's HESS

4.2 Flexibility availability communication using dataspace

The Push mechanism and the blockchain features developed within InterSTORE explained in D2.8, are two of the main advancements beyond the state of the art in this area. Three new developments were done in total in the project in this regard. The first was the release of the Open-source user interface, the second the push mechanism and the third the ability to publish the data transactions registries in a blockchain, which is a distributed ledger also known as DLT (distributed ledger technologies).

The current state of the art of dataspace connectors, allowed users to share data by creating services/folders, to which other participants in the data space can subscribe to and download that data. In this model, the user who creates the service acts as the data provider, while the subscribers act as data consumers. So far, the connector only allowed a data consumer to make a GET request (download) data from the consumer. However, this environment became a limitation when other use cases were considered. There are a number of cases in which the creator of the service, could have the need to receive information from third-parties without knowledge of its existence. Hence, the need to create a mechanism that could allow

a subscriber of a service, to push data (post) and provide spontaneously files to that interested party. The creator of the service acknowledges that it wants to receive data from several subscribers at their own discretion and responsibility.

In the electricity domain, such scenario can be better understood with the flexibility availability provision. The creator of the service (an Aggregator) becomes available to several subscribers, to receive bids or simply flexibility availability of their assets, that can be later activated. The flexibility providers can hence, publish/push or post this information in the Aggregator's service spontaneously at its most convenient time.

In this regard, given that failure to deliver the provided flexibility availability, may mean incurring in penalties, an agreement via blockchain is desirable. This is because in case of disagreement between the two parties, both can refer to an untampered registry of data transactions, without suspicious of conflict of interest. This conflict of interest could occur, given that the aggregator (or a non-trusted party) could be the host of the dataspace itself and have control over the timeline (dataspace log files). Under this rationale, the development of the blockchain registry option, was developed for the InterSTORE project, making it the first of its kind, within the dataspace domain. The blockchain used at the moment is a very low fee public chain, called Polygon, which is a second layer of the popular Ethereum network. To summarize the two developments, these entail the following:

Push mechanism- Users are now able not only to get data from a data provider created service but instead spontaneously send (Push) data to that same service. This new feature unlocks new use cases and it has already been tested within the project between InescTEC and CyberGrid with the support of Engineering. The use case focused on providing flexibility availability to an open call by an aggregator. The flexibility provider (InescTEC) provides the availability for the next day, from a set of hybrid storage system, to the aggregator (Cyber-Grid) service.

Blockchain registry - The same use case made use of the blockchain feature, which when enabled, registers in a public blockchain (the Polygon network), the exchange of information. This is an important option for critical data transactions, when potential penalties might arise, such as the lack of service delivery due to miscommunication or loss of information. In this case, mitigating any conflict of interest, the log files of the transactions can be consulted and any doubts clarified in an untampered and transparent registry. This can be done by checking the Amoy explorer (<https://www.oklink.com/amoy/tx-list>), used in this specific case.

The new version can be found open-source here: <https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Inter-STORE/Data-Space-Connector>.

The battery system used to assess the flexibility is shown in the [Figure 21](#) below. It is comprised of a 100 kW, 100 kWh Lithium Battery and a Vanadium battery of 10 kW and 40 kWh capacity.

Figure 21: HESS providing the flexibility availability to the aggregator's service

The demonstration of this feature was done exploring the use case of flexibility availability provision. In this case, a flexibility service provider sends every day its assets' flexibility for the next day.

The demonstration was done between InescTEC (flexibility provider) and CyberGRID (Aggregator) with the technical support of Engineering.

In order to enable the push option, we first set up the .env file enabling the optional feature of the push mechanism (Push_Enabled=) to TRUE as can be seen in the [Figure 22](#) below:

```

salvador.carvalho@cc-rpes  x  +  -  Mut
GNU nano 6.2 .env
# Indicates the number of subpart attribute for a data part entity
# Default 15
LOCAL_API_DATA_SUBPART_NUMBER=150

# Notarization service configuration
NOTARIZATION_ENABLED=false
NOTARIZATION_PROTOCOL=http
NOTARIZATION_HOST=blockchain-notarization
NOTARIZATION_PORT=8092
NOTARIZATION_PATH=/api/contracts
NOTARIZATION_NETWORK=80002
# Wallet address
NOTARIZATION_OWNER=0x5438e9ca864a56d05e3Ae255F17f1067a47c5454
# prefix list used to filter entities that have to create a smart contract, use comma(,) as separator. If empty the filter is disabled
NOTARIZATION_PREFIX_FILTER_LIST=urn:ngsi-ld:dataentity:,

# Blockchain configuration
SERVER_PORT=8092
SEPOLIA_API_KEY=your_sepolia_api_key
MUMBAI_API_KEY=https://polygon-mumbai.g.alchemy.com/v2/v6PnkHxMlsvt0xCP3_U7a36BYZBHC16j
AMOY_API_KEY=https://polygon-amoy.g.alchemy.com/v2/8s71lkBFYwk6TQR:BfN9wdJduLpVGb3D
MNEMONIC=energy desk gaze essay gadget impulse swing treat safe pipe discover slab

# API Url Configuration (centralized services). Not use localhost or 127.0.0.1, use the local IP address
API_URL=https://smart-energy.eng.it/api

# Push scenario: use true to enable, false to disable
PUSH_ENABLED=true

^G Help      ^O Write Out  ^W Where Is   ^K Cut        ^T Execute    ^G Location   ^U Undo       ^M Set Mark
^X Exit      ^R Read File  ^\ Replace    ^P Paste      ^_ Justify    ^/ Go To Line ^= Redo       ^= Copy

```

Figure 22: Configuration file set up enabling the push mechanism as True/False

Once this option is chosen, a service can be created and subscribed as a normal one, under this option of “push”. In the demonstration CyberGRID created this service and InescTEC subscribed to it, and data started to be shared. The data exchanged in the demonstration was a test file using the UI but since then made automatically in the back-end. The file here seen in

the timeline (logfile of the data exchanges) as test4 in [Figure 23](#). Note that the exchange timestamp is marked at 11:38am provided by InescTEC.

The screenshot from the connector UI, shows the log file/timeline containing the data transaction registry. One can observe that the data exchange occurred. Once it is here it is published automatically in the blockchain.

Figure 23: Timeline registry from the data transaction from the demonstration

Each registry has an ID assigned for the transaction and along with the time stamp. This will be required to confirm and identify the transaction in the blockchain Amoy Testnet explorer.

This Amoy explorer is shown in [Figure 24](#). The line showing a transaction at 11:38:35 with method Sanleo highlighted with the blue rectangle, is the one corresponding to the demonstrated transaction, which resulted in a 0.00999437 POL associated cost. This registry is public and can be consulted by anyone.

Transaction ID	Method	Registry ID	Timestamp	From Address	To Address	Gas Used	Cost (POL)
0x6af9f993c32d...	sanleo	17432642	01/29/2025, 11:38:37	0xa865...8e3d77fb	0x6d94...467975	0 POL	0.13805438 POL
0x90e5c381f17c...	transmit	17432642	01/29/2025, 11:38:37	0x32df...c4e75e3d	0xebe9...9211a0	0 POL	0.00394605 POL
0x26cdf74d5ae...	mint	17432641	01/29/2025, 11:38:35	0x78e4...0b600ca4	0x095e...8bd389	0 POL	0.00146187 POL
0x6b8e150bff89...	approve	17432641	01/29/2025, 11:38:35	0x1be7...33b96f49	0x7551...636482b	0 POL	0.0008617 POL
0xbeeae193dafd...	sanleo	17432641	01/29/2025, 11:38:35	0x5438...a47c5454	0xafea...9750f1	0 POL	0.00999437 POL
0xbe201d85d0f...	0x00164c99	17432641	01/29/2025, 11:38:35	0xb837...6d16d2dd	0xff00...00042069	0 POL	0.00072692 POL
0x1f7784564fde...	POL transfer	17432640	01/29/2025, 11:38:33	0x1f9f...66611638	0x6886...2acace9cb	3 POL	0.00064921 POL
0xbfc980620e65...	processOrder	17432640	01/29/2025, 11:38:33	0x5855...7ef84e42	0x589c...e38bec	0 POL	0.00382379 POL

Figure 24: Logfile of the transaction directly from the polygon blockchain

The Amoy testnet explorer shown in [Figure 25](#), further provides the chance to access other information such as the block and the transaction ID.

The screenshot displays the Amoy Testnet explorer interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the OKLINK logo and menu items: Explorer, Onchain AML, Chaintelligence, APIs, EaaS, and a search bar. The main header includes the Amoy Testnet explorer logo, a Faucet button, and navigation links for Home, Blockchain, Developers, and More. An advertisement for OKX DEX is visible below the header. The main content area is titled 'Transaction details' and shows a transaction hash: 0xb6eae193dafd5078f2f4f3da33d282815cb7e5504bdb21dcad18a75c82462faa. Below the hash are two tabs: 'Overview' (selected) and 'Event logs'. The transaction status is 'Success'. The block number is 17432641 with 45 block confirmations. The timestamp is 01/29/2025, 11:38:35 (1 min ago). An advertisement for OKX DEX is also present at the bottom of the transaction details section.

Figure 25: Details from the blockchain in the Amoy explorer

The demonstration was successful and clearly show-cased the use case of flexibility availability provision, which could further be explored to market options or bilateral agreements, leveraging on both the push mechanism and DLT.

5 Conclusions

The InterSTORE data space demonstrates the potential of connected data ecosystems in creating value across multiple energy assets and services. By leveraging datasets and fostering collaboration among industry stakeholders, it sets a precedent for advanced energy optimization and sustainable practices.

This report highlights the development and implementation of methodologies aimed at optimizing data valorisation within connected data spaces, with a focus on improving user acceptance and enhancing the sustainability of energy systems. By leveraging real-world operational data, advanced analytical frameworks, and scenario-based optimization, the case studies presented illustrate how data sharing can create value for multiple stakeholders across the energy value chain.

The PV Valorisation Tool (3.1) demonstrated how benchmarking photovoltaic (PV) system performance against tailored standards enables users to identify inefficiencies, optimize energy output, and make informed investment decisions. This approach not only empowers users to maximize renewable energy production but also supports transparency and accountability, particularly for organizations managing multiple installations.

The HESS Optimization (3.2) case study provided compelling evidence of the economic and environmental advantages of hybrid energy storage systems. By integrating diverse storage technologies and employing advanced optimization models, HESS configurations outperformed traditional systems in terms of cost-efficiency, emission reduction, and operational longevity. This work underscores the transformative potential of hybrid systems in addressing the challenges of renewable energy integration and grid stability.

The Green EV Ranking (3.3) initiative showcased the importance of aligning EV charging practices with environmental objectives. By utilizing carbon intensity data to optimize charging schedules, the tool provides actionable insights that reduce emissions and improve the sustainability of EV operations. The ranking system further promotes transparency and competition among organizations striving to enhance their environmental performance.

The anomaly detection case (3.4), leveraged on operational data from batteries and provides an unsupervised machine learning approach to detect anomalies in battery operation. Given the cost of obtaining faulty observations from such systems, the opportunity to validate and complement training with other systems observations can be very valuable. This case shows just how this type of data can be used and shared.

The limitations of such cases lie on the willingness to share data and on the labelling of the data being shared. Systems are often in the local language and use different units and terms to refer to the same variable. In this regard semantic and syntactic interoperability is advised. Assets should be related to each other in order to have a common thread for value extraction. It should be highlighted the unleashed potential of the new features of the InterSTORE connector. These are the push mechanism and the blockchain publication option. The fact that a user can have a passive approach in collecting data, allows for market-like interactions. This is even more important when the transparent publication of such data transactions is made with a distributed ledger technology.

Looking forward, the methodologies and tools developed within this framework have the potential to scale across diverse applications, from residential and commercial energy users to large-scale energy operators. By promoting trust, transparency, and the demonstrable value of data sharing, this work lays a solid foundation for the widespread adoption of innovative energy solutions. Ultimately, it underscores the role of data as a strategic enabler for building resilient, efficient, and environmentally responsible energy ecosystems.

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